

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF VILLAGE LIFE THROUGH PROVIDING ADEQUATE PUBLIC FACILITIES IN TLOGOSARI VILLAGE

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ABSTRACT

Village infrastructure development, such as in Tlogosari Village, is very important to improve the quality of life of the community. The government has a primary role in providing resources, while communities are responsible for maintaining facilities. Repairing the futsal field and installing road signs in Tlogosari Village are concrete examples of sustainable development that involve the active role of the government and community. Based on the situation analysis above, the aim of this service is to improve the quality of life of the community through "Improving the Quality of Village Life by Providing Adequate Public Facilities in Tlogosari Village". The Asset Based Community Development (ABCD) approach focuses on inventorying community assets to support empowerment. The KKN program in Tlogosari Village utilizes this approach to improve infrastructure such as futsal fields and installing road signs. The evaluation shows success in improving the quality of life of the community, although there are several improvements that need to be made. This evaluation method is carried out qualitatively. The data taken was collected through the results of community service student meetings and interviews with the community and also Tlogosari village officials. Making road signs in Tlogosari Village at six hamlet boundary points and repairing the futsal field, including making bamboo goals, aims to increase functionality and safety. Despite their success, both faced logistical and material challenges. The concept of Asset Based Community Development (ABCD) and the principles of sustainable development are the basis for implementing this activity.

Keywords: *Quality of Village Life, Public Facilities, Tlogosari Village*

I. INTRODUCTION

Considering that villages are an integral part of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, infrastructure development in villages is the focus of the government (Riskayanti, 2022). Building a village means building the majority of Indonesia's

population. A village can be defined as a community that lives side by side with certain legal, organizational, and geographical boundaries. Village geography can describe a village decorated with rice fields and fields of shared life (Dimas et al., n.d.). Tlogosari Village is a village located in Bondowoso Regency. This village has a population of around 5,691 people, the majority of whom work as farmers. Tlogosari Village is located in a mountainous area that is quite easy to reach, so access to resources is very good. The assets that we studied and repaired in Tlogosari Village were the repair of the futsal field on the uneven or perforated part of the field. Making a goal made of bamboo because the previous goal was damaged. Repairing the faded field lines (Budiman & Hadyansah, 2021). Repairing the futsal field on uneven or perforated parts of the field, making goals made of bamboo, repairing faded field lines, and making and installing road signs to indicate the boundaries of the hamlets in Tlogosari village (Dasar & Desa, n.d.).

In the community service carried out by Maryati et al. (2022), regarding "Mapping of Public and Social Facilities as a Basis for Development Planning in Raku Village, North Tabukan District, Sangihe Islands Regency, North Sulawesi Province". The purpose of community service is to map public and social facilities, find out the distribution of public and social facilities in the village, and provide spatial data as a basis for policy-making by the government. The approach used is the field survey integration method and spatial data analysis. The results obtained from this study, namely, Public and Social Facilities and general analysis of spatial data, show that public and social facilities in Raku village are divided into educational facilities, health facilities, worship facilities, government offices, and other social facilities. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities, repairing and providing public facilities Differences: The materials used in the study are different, the research subjects are different, and the methods used in the study are different.

In the community service carried out by Dimas et al. (n.d.), on "Public Perception of Public Facilities in Pakusari Village, Sumber Pinang Hamlet". The results obtained from this study are that although there are educational facilities, the quality of education in this village may still need to be improved, and challenges such as the lack of trained teachers and the lack of supporting facilities may need to be addressed. The infrastructure in Pakusari Village is said to be lacking, several public facilities that should be good including main roads, electricity networks, clean water, and health services such as hospitals and pharmacies still have shortcomings in terms of accessibility and quality of this infrastructure. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities Differences: The materials used in the study are different, the research subjects are different, and the methods used in the study are different. Community service was carried out by Dayanti & Kusuma (2023), on "Improving the Volleyball Court to Improve School Integrity and Improve Student Skills and Achievements in the Field of Sports at SMP Negeri 2 Tapalang Barat. The results obtained after the implementation of this improvement activity are evident from the change in field conditions which can be used properly by students of SMPN 2 Tapalang Barat. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities, repairing and providing public facilities, the same research subjects Differences: The materials used in the research are different,

and the methods used in the research are different. In the community service carried out by Maulana (2018), on "The Range of Public Facilities and Social Facilities for Developer Housing Based on Road Network Patterns in Lowokwaru District, Malang City". The purpose of the community service is to determine the range of public facilities and social facilities for developer housing based on the shape of the road network pattern. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities Differences: The materials used in the research are different, the research subjects are different and the methods used in the research are different.

In the community service carried out by Nurcahyo et al. (2021), regarding "Criteria in Selecting Priorities for the Development of Public and Social Facilities in Sustainable Housing". The purpose of the community service is to focus on the decision to select priorities for public and social facilities. The results obtained from this study show that the criteria for selecting priorities for the development of public and social facilities in sustainable housing are in sequence, namely Land/Land Use, Environment, Transportation & Communication, Social, and Economy. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities, and different research subjects Differences: The materials used in the research are different, the research subjects are different and the methods used in the research are different. In the community service carried out by Pratama et al. (2022), regarding "Implementation of the Kukerta Program to Create Road Boundary Signs between Hamlets as an Effort to Provide Information". The purpose of the community service is to make it easier for the public to know the boundaries of each hamlet, and making these hamlet boundary nameplates, can provide benefits as road signs. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities, the same research subjects, repairing and providing public facilities for road signs. Differences: The materials used in the research are different, and the methods used in the research are different.

In the community service carried out by Ningrum et al. (2019), on "Making Village Facilities for Village Road Signs and the Environment of Jogosatru Village". The results obtained from this study, namely the manufacture and installation of these road sign boards or plaques, are a form of participation, coordination, and active involvement of students, lecturers, and residents of the surrounding village. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities, the same research subjects, repairing and providing public facilities for road signs. Differences: The materials used in the research are different, and the methods used in the research are different.

In the community service carried out by Tanjung et al. (2022), on "Repairing and Making Street Name Signs and Location Plans in Gerbang Sari Village". The purpose of the community service is to facilitate road access to the hamlets in Gerbang Sari Village. The results obtained from this study in the process of activities from preparation to implementation of the program, no significant obstacles were found. In addition, based on 3 indicators of the survey of the level of satisfaction of the community and village visitors with the procurement and installation of road signs, it shows that the community is satisfied with the program. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities, repairing and providing public facilities for road signs. Differences: The materials used in the study are different, the research subjects are different and the methods used in the study are different.

In the community service carried out by Apriani & Priyono (2022), regarding "Making Hamlet Road Direction Signs in Muhammadiyah Aisyiyah KKN Activities in Keru Village". The purpose of the community service is to make it easier for the community to know the boundaries. The approach used consists of 4 (four) stages, namely initial location survey, determining the initial location for installing the board, preparing tools and materials, making and painting the board, and finally installing the board. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities, the research subjects are the same, repairing and providing public facilities for road signs. The materials used in the study are the same. Differences: The methods used in the study are different.

In the community service carried out by Fachruddin Haryadi et al. (2022), regarding "Making Street Nameplates for RW 01 Kel. Antang, Kec. Manggala, Makassar City". The results obtained from this study, namely by making street nameplates in Kampung Baru RW.01 located in Antang Village, Manggala District, Makassar City, are expected to help both residents and residents from outside the area to make it easier to find the address they are looking for. Similarities: Discussing Public Facilities, repairing and providing public facilities for road signs. Differences: The materials used in this study are different, the research subjects are different and the methods used in the study are different.

Pie chart

Based on the analysis of potential data shown by previous studies, road signs are the dominant and potentially positive part of the community, while the futsal field research area shows a very small percentage. Meanwhile, the high public interest in futsal sports is very large and has the potential for the growth of the sports industry in this area. However, the relatively small percentage of public facilities needs attention. The lack of green open space and other public facilities can have an impact on the quality of life of the community and reduce the attractiveness of the area for

various age groups. The results of this study are in line with previous studies that show an increasing trend in public interest in sports. And also the importance of road signs for the community. To improve the quality of life of the community and develop the area sustainably.

This study offers a fresh perspective by combining analysis of road signs and futsal fields. The combination of these two elements has not been widely studied in previous studies, especially in the context of development and renovation as we carried out in Tlogosari village. Thus, this study is expected to provide new contributions to the field of regional planning studies, especially in understanding the dynamics of land use and visual communication in public spaces.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study uses the Asset-Based Community Development (ABCD) approach (Evi Nurus Suroiyah & Sholihatul Atik Hikmawati, 2021) to study and develop public facilities in the form of road signs and futsal field improvements. ABCD is a method that focuses on identifying and mobilizing local assets for community development (Kretzman, J. P., and McKnight, 1993).

Asset Based Communities Development (ABCD) is an approach model in community development. This approach emphasizes the inventory of assets in the community that are considered to support community empowerment activities. The emphasis on asset reinventing is the hallmark of this approach because in asset reinventing students are required to explore the availability of social assets owned by the community. Synchronization between the availability of social assets and the KKN work program determines the success of ABCD (Yuwana, 2022).

The process of building a community that begins with the process of finding assets, skills, and capacities of residents, community associations, and local institutions is the concept of the Asset Based Community Development (ABCD) method. 4 foundations can develop an asset-based community (ABCD), the 4 foundations are:

- a) Focusing on assets and strengths (potential), no problems or issues faced by the community.
- b) Identifying and mobilizing (moving) assets, skills, and interests of individuals and the community (community).
- c) Encouraged to build a community from the inside out.
- d) Driven by relationships (relationship-driven) (Ahmad, 2007)

The ABCD method used in allocating village resources has been determined by the community, not by the government or organization (sponsor/community-driven). Therefore, the community remains the controller even though it requires or cooperates with other partnerships (government). The author chose the ABCD method because the ABCD method involves the community in recognizing and utilizing their potential, and the results of the program tend to be more sustainable. This method encourages the community to continue to innovate and develop their village independently. The ABCD method focuses on the potential and strengths of the village, while the PAR method only identifies problems that exist in the village.

The subjects of this study include local communities, youth groups using futsal fields, village governments, and community leaders. The selection of these subjects is based on the principle of inclusive participation in ABCD (Mathie & Cunningham, 2003).

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Road Sign Making

A road sign is a nameplate containing data or information that is installed in a border area, and provides information to local residents and the outside community as an identity of the residential area (Pratama et al., 2022). The making of road signs is a very important process in ensuring the safety and smoothness of traffic in an area. Without clear and effective road signs, drivers can experience confusion that has the potential to cause accidents or congestion. In this journal, we will discuss how the making of road signs has provided significant benefits to the people of Tlogosari Village in facilitating navigation for residents and visitors, as well as increasing awareness of the importance of access to accurate local information.

With the activity of making road signs, there are several benefits obtained by the community, including as a sign of direction, warning, and information that makes it easier for drivers to adapt to road conditions and traffic regulations (Nyoman Suparsa et al., 2023). The following are the results of community service carried out in Tlogosari Village, Bondowoso Regency, which include field surveys of materials, making signs, painting signs, and finally installing signs at 6 points on the borders between hamlets in Tlogosari Village. Road signs were made at 6 points on the borders between hamlets in Tlogosari Village. Each sign displays the name of the hamlet and RT/RW. The purpose of making road signs is to make it easier for residents to know the boundaries of the hamlets in Tlogosari Village. This activity involves the Village Government and the local community as providers of materials.

Table of Materials for Making Road Signs

No	Material Name	Size	Result
1	Bamboo	2 meters x 6	6 Road Signs
2	Plywood	1 sheet	
3	Wire	1kg	
4	Nails	½ kg	
5	Paint	½ kg	
6	Spray paint/Pylox	1 Can	
7	Writing Paper	8 Sheets	

Previous research results on public and social facilities in Raku Village showed that various facilities supported community life, including educational facilities, health, worship, government offices, and other social facilities. Meanwhile, in Tlogosari Village, there was an initiative to create road signs at six points on the border between hamlets to make it easier for residents to recognize regional boundaries. These two projects have different scales and focus; Raku Village focuses

on providing various public facilities to improve the quality of life of the community at large, while Tlogosari Village implements specific projects with detailed processes, from needs analysis to evaluation, despite facing several technical obstacles such as access to the material collection and soil conditions. Although different in approach and scale, these two initiatives reflect efforts to improve the welfare and comfort of village communities through improving infrastructure and regional orientation (Maryati et al., 2022). The results of previous research journals show the implementation of different community projects but both aim to improve village infrastructure. In Sungai Selari Village, activities that were not specifically described were reported to have run smoothly and on target according to the specified time, receiving positive recognition from the community and village officials. Meanwhile, in Tlogosari Village, the project focused on making road signs at six points between hamlets, to make it easier for residents to recognize hamlet boundaries. The Tlogosari project involved a more detailed process, from needs analysis to evaluation, using weather-resistant materials. Although both projects were considered successful, the Tlogosari project faced specific challenges such as difficulty in accessing bamboo and rocky soil conditions. The main difference lies in the level of detail in the reporting; the Sungai Selari project emphasized general success, while the Tlogosari project provided a more detailed picture of the process and obstacles faced. However, both projects reflect positive efforts in developing village infrastructure with community participation and recognition (Pratama et al., 2022).

A comparison between the Research on Making Village Facilities for Road Signs in Jogosatru Village and the road sign-making activity in Tlogosari Village shows differences in approach and focus. The research in Jogosatru Village emphasized participatory and collaborative aspects, involving students, teachers, and villagers in the process of making and installing road signs, reflecting a community-based development approach. Meanwhile, activities in Tlogosari Village have a more structured and technical approach, with the placement of signs at six strategic points on the borders between hamlets. The process in Tlogosari involved systematic stages from needs analysis to evaluation, with a focus on functional aspects such as material durability and readability. Despite facing technical challenges such as access to materials and soil conditions, the activities in Tlogosari succeeded in achieving their goals. The main difference lies in the focus of Jogosatru Village on participatory processes and community empowerment, while Tlogosari Village emphasizes more on the physical results and functionality of the signs, although both aim to improve village infrastructure (Ningrum et al., 2019).

The first step we took in determining one of our work programs, namely making road signs, was to survey several hamlets in Tlogosari Village, as well as visit the homes of several hamlets. During the survey, we did not find any useful signs to provide information on which hamlets we had passed. That is why we decided to make road signs. Before that, we also asked about the Hamlet border points.

The next step is to determine and prepare what materials are needed to make road signs. The materials needed include plywood purchased at a nearby hardware store and the measurement process is carried out directly on-site, bamboo as a

support obtained from residents, paint used to beautify the appearance of the sign, also white spray paint to clarify the writing, wire and nails used to connect the bamboo supports and also plywood.

After all the materials are available, the manufacturing process continues, which includes painting the road signs, writing the contents of the road signs, and forming the road signs. The manufacturing process is carried out in stages for approximately 4 days. In the process of installing the road signs, we were assisted by village officials. The process of installing the road signs starts with Sempolan Hamlet, then Gentong Hamlet, Krajan Hamlet, Laok Gunung Hamlet, and finally Panggang Hamlet in the evening. The end of the implementation of this work program is the evaluation. In the evaluation, we discussed a lot of the shortcomings that occurred in this work program. As a material for improvement in subsequent work programs. Finally, road sign maintenance is an important part of the entire process. After being installed, road signs must be checked periodically to ensure that they remain in good condition. Checks include checking for physical damage, blurring of text or symbols, and the reflectivity of the sign. If damage or deficiencies are found, repairs or replacement of the sign need to be carried out immediately to ensure that the information conveyed remains accurate and effective. With proper maintenance, road signs will continue to function properly, maintaining safety and smooth traffic flow.

The activity of making road signs in Tlogosari Village is an effort to improve residents' orientation towards hamlet boundaries. From the program of installing road signs indicating the direction of the hamlet road carried out by KKN Posko 20 UIN KHAS Jember students together with several Tlogosari Village officials, a survey was conducted to determine the location for installing road signs in the direction of entry and exit from the hamlet in Tlogosari Village (Pratama et al., 2022). Road signs were installed at six points on the border between hamlets, using bamboo and plywood so that they were easy to read. The process of making signs involves several stages, namely needs analysis, procurement of materials, manufacturing, and evaluation. Although this activity was successfully implemented, there were several obstacles in the process, such as difficulty in accessing the bamboo collection location and rocky soil conditions.

As KKN UIN KHAS Jember students, we encourage and raise awareness among the community for the sustainability of the program to maintain and care for the signs so that the program that has been implemented is successful and useful for the local community. Of course, this is determined by the people of Tlogosari Village itself, road users, and people who visit Tlogosari Village to utilize the infrastructure. To increase public knowledge and awareness in making this program a success, the community is given the trust to maintain and care for the facilities that are part of the KKN student program so that in the future Tlogosari Village can become a prosperous village, especially in terms of providing infrastructure for hamlet road directions (Apriani & Priyono, 2022).

Figure 1 and 2. Road Sign Making Process

3.2 Futsal Field Repair

Futsal field repair is an important step to ensure the quality of the game and player safety. A high-quality futsal field not only improves the playing experience but also extends the life of the field itself (Ardiansah & Hidayatullah, 2022). One of the main aspects of repair is the maintenance of the field surface. A flat surface free from damage such as holes or cracks is essential to prevent injuries and ensure the ball moves well. Therefore, regular inspection and immediate repair of minor damage can avoid bigger problems in the future (Zainuddin et al., 2022).

The cleanliness of the futsal field should also be a major focus in the repair process. Dust, dirt, and other material residues can affect the performance of the field surface and reduce grip (Prabowo, 2020). By carrying out routine cleaning and good waste management, the condition of the field will be maintained. Using the right cleaning tools and the right techniques can help keep the field clean and functional. Finally, the aesthetic aspect also plays a role in futsal field repair. Faded or peeling field line paint needs to be renewed to meet the standards of the game. In addition, the addition of facilities such as goal repairs can improve the experience for all parties involved. One of the facilities and infrastructure used for training is the goal. A goal is an obstacle made by humans or naturally. In a football match, the use of goals is very important in the game, because the goal is a means used to determine whether or not the ball is kicked or headed towards the goal (Suryamen et al., 2016). With attention to these details, the futsal field will not only function well but also provide a pleasant atmosphere for players and spectators. The futsal field repair project will include several important stages to ensure quality and comfort of use. First, the damaged field surface will be repaired by re-leveling and replacing cracked or perforated parts. The material used is a type of high-quality synthetic flooring that is

durable and non-slippery, to prevent injury. Furthermore, the field lines will be repainted using special paint that is durable and has a contrasting color, ensuring that the lines remain clearly visible even though they are used in the long term. In addition, the project also includes the creation of bamboo goals. Bamboo was chosen as the main material because it has good durability and is environmentally friendly. The goals will be designed and installed solidly, ensuring stability during the game. The use of bamboo also gives a natural and aesthetic touch to the field, creating a more traditional and attractive atmosphere.

Goal Making Materials Table

No	Material Name	Size	Result
1	Bamboo	36 meters	2 Goals
2	Wire	½ kg	
3	Nails	½ kg	
4	Rubber Inner tube	20 Pieces	
5	Outer Tube		

Previous research results Both results show efforts to improve sports facilities with different focuses and scales. At SMPN 2 Tapalang Barat, the field improvement activities resulted in significant changes, making the field more suitable for use by students, although specific details of the improvements were not mentioned. Meanwhile, the futsal field improvement project involved a series of more detailed actions, including surface repairs, repainting lines, and making environmentally friendly bamboo goals. This project aims to improve the quality and safety of the field but faces challenges such as the availability of quality bamboo, assembly difficulties, and weather effects. Although both projects aim to improve sports facilities, the futsal field improvement appears to be more complex in its implementation and faces more specific challenges compared to the field improvement at SMPN 2 Tapalang Barat. However, both projects reflect a commitment to improving the quality of sports facilities for their users (Dayanti & Kusuma, 2023).

The two research results show different approaches to the development and improvement of futsal fields. The first research design proposes the concept of Baja Masuk Desa (BMD) for the construction of a futsal field sports arena, with a focus on the use of steel structures. This approach aims to optimize the use of iron ore natural resources, improve the effectiveness of building structures, and introduce steel technology in rural areas. This design involves the use of IWF and H-beam iron, concrete pillars with power plate foundations, and a superstructure system with a portal frame. On the other hand, the second futsal field improvement project adopted a simpler and more environmentally friendly approach, focusing on surface repair, repainting lines, and making bamboo goals. Although the goal of both projects is to improve the quality and safety of the field, the first approach is more complex and oriented towards structural innovation, while the second approach is more practical and faces implementation challenges such as material availability and weather effects.

These differences reflect variations in the scale, resources, and local context of each sports facility development project (Zakaria Umar et al., 2022). Both initiatives aim to improve the infrastructure and comfort of the village community, but with different scales and focuses. Field revitalization is a more comprehensive project, involving spatial planning, drainage systems, flood control, and greening, which requires expert planning and long-term collaboration between the village government and universities. On the other hand, the construction of road signs in Tlogosari Village is a more focused and practical project, aiming to improve the orientation of residents by marking the boundaries of the hamlet at six points. Although the scale of the project is smaller, the construction of road signs also requires careful planning, from needs analysis to evaluation, and addresses technical challenges such as access to materials and soil conditions. Both projects demonstrate how village development initiatives can vary in scale and complexity, but both require careful planning and community involvement to achieve the goal of improving the quality of life of villagers (Hartanto & Yuwono, 2009).

The improvement of the futsal field aims to improve the quality and safety of the facility by involving surface repair, repainting of lines, and the construction of environmentally friendly bamboo goals. This project faced several challenges, including the availability of quality bamboo, difficulties in assembly, and the effects of weather on materials and work processes. This effort is expected to provide the final result in the form of a better, safer, and more sustainable futsal field, while also overcoming various obstacles that arise during its implementation (Lutfiyatul et al., 2013).

The community service activities that we carried out during the KKN field improvement period went smoothly and according to plan. Based on the discussion in this journal, it can be concluded that this activity is very helpful and beneficial for the people of Tlogosari Village. In addition to providing new insights and knowledge, it also creates productive time by not wasting free time on less beneficial activities. Through this activity, the free time that the community has, especially teenagers. It is hoped that through this activity, the community can apply the knowledge that has been obtained during this program in everyday life.

Figure 3 and 4. Goal Making Process

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The activity of making road signs in Tlogosari Village was carried out at six points on the borders between hamlets. This sign aims to make it easier for residents to recognize hamlet boundaries, with weather-resistant and easy-to-read materials. The manufacturing process involves needs analysis, procurement of materials, manufacturing, and evaluation. Although this activity was successful, there were several obstacles such as difficult access to bamboo and rocky soil texture.

Meanwhile, the repair of the futsal field involved repairing the surface, repainting the lines, and making goals from environmentally friendly bamboo. The aim is to improve the quality and safety of the field. In its implementation, this project faced challenges such as the availability of quality bamboo, difficulties in assembly, and the influence of weather.

The discussion of the implementation of this activity can be analyzed using the concept of Asset Based Community Development (ABCD) which emphasizes asset-based development, where communities are encouraged to utilize their local potential. ABCD principles such as focusing on assets, participation, and partnerships are the foundation for mobilizing the community. In addition, the theory of sustainable development and development economics are also relevant in understanding this effort, emphasizing the importance of balance between the economy, environment, and society, as well as the involvement of government and communities in realizing sustainable and inclusive development.

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